

STUDENTS' WRITING SKILLS AND SELF-EFFICACY THROUGH THE COOPERATIVE INTEGRATED READING AND COMPOSITION (CIRC) MODEL USING PICTURE SERIES MEDIA AT SMK NEGERI 3 KEPAHANG

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ABSTRACT

This study was conducted due to the low level of students' writing skills and self-efficacy. Writing skills include content, organization, vocabulary, grammar, and mechanics, while self-efficacy consists of magnitude, strength, and generality. This study aimed to determine the differences between the CIRC model assisted by picture series media, the CIRC model without media, and conventional learning on students' writing skills and self-efficacy at SMK Negeri 3 Kepahiang. This research employed a quantitative approach with a quasi-experimental design. The sample consisted of three classes of tenth-grade students: the Motorcycle Engineering (TSM) class as the CIRC class with picture series media, the Visual Communication Design (DKV) class as the CIRC class without media, and the class of accounting as the conventional learning class. Data were collected through a writing test (pretest–post-tests) and a self-efficacy questionnaire. The data were analysed to examine differences in outcomes among the classes and were tested using the Kruskal–Wallis H test. The results indicated that there were differences in students' writing skills and self-efficacy. The CIRC class with picture series media showed a significant difference compared to the CIRC class without media and the conventional class.

Keywords: CIRC, Picture Series Media, Writing Skills, Self-Efficacy, Quasi-Experimental.

INTRODUCTION

English is an international language that functions as a global means of communication in various fields, such as education, technology, economics, and culture. In Indonesia, English holds an important position in the educational curriculum and is taught at various levels of schooling (Defhany et al., 2025). One of the essential competencies in learning English is writing skills. Writing is a complex language skill because it involves the ability to develop ideas, organize thoughts logically, and convey information systematically (Mega Januarti Putri & Wahyu Sudewi, 2023). Moreover, in the context of 21st-century learning, writing skills are also closely related to critical thinking, communication, and collaboration abilities (Dedi Aprianto et al., 2025).

However, students' writing skills are still relatively low. Observations conducted at SMK Negeri 3 Kepahiang indicate that many students experience difficulties in developing ideas, organizing coherent paragraphs, and expressing their thoughts in English. Data from the Final Semester Assessment (PAT) for the 2024/2025 academic year show that 73.17% of students scored below the Minimum Mastery Criterion (70). The main weaknesses were found in the aspects of idea development, sentence coherence, and completeness of content (Maryan, 2025). In addition to cognitive factors, writing ability is also influenced by psychological factors, one of which is self-efficacy. According to social cognitive theory, self-efficacy refers to an individual's belief in their ability to accomplish specific tasks (Asmaul et al., 2025). Students with high self-efficacy tend to be more confident and persistent in completing writing tasks.

RESEARCH METHOD

Research has shown that series picture media can improve the quality of students' writing because they help enrich content, improve text structure, and expand vocabulary (Rismayanti, 2021). Therefore, the implementation of a cooperative learning model such as Cooperative Integrated Reading and Composition (CIRC) combined with visual media can create a more interactive learning environment and support students' cognitive and emotional development.

This study employed a quantitative approach using a quasi-experimental design with a non-equivalent control group design to examine the differences in students' writing skills and self-efficacy after receiving different treatments. The research subjects consisted of two experimental classes and one control class, each of which was given a pre-test and post-test. The first experimental class was taught using the CIRC model assisted by series picture media, the second experimental class used the CIRC model without media, while the control class was taught using conventional learning methods. The research was conducted in the odd semester of the 2025/2026 academic year at SMK Negeri 3 Kepahiang, involving tenth-grade students from the TSM, DKV, and accounting departments. The sample was selected using a purposive sampling technique by considering the equivalence of students' academic abilities.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This research was conducted at SMK Negeri 3 Kepahiang, located in Bermani Ilir District, Kepahiang Regency, in Gunung Agung Village. The sample groups consisted of tenth-grade students from three departments: Grade 10 Motorcycle Engineering as the experimental class using the CIRC model with media, Grade 10 Visual Communication Design as the experimental class using the CIRC model without media, and Grade 10 Accounting as the control class in the 2025/2026 academic year. This study aims to examine the differences in students' writing skills and self-efficacy among those who participated in learning using the CIRC model with media, the CIRC model without media, and conventional learning at SMK Negeri 3 Kepahiang.

Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics of students' writing skills.

	N	Min	Max	Mean	S. D
Pre-Test Writing Skills (CIRC with Picture Series)	29	15	35	25.69	4.950
Post-Test Writing Skills (CIRC with Picture Series)	29	70	90	82.41	6.068
Pre-Test Writing Skills (CIRC without Picture Series)	29	15	45	28.97	9.198
Post-Test Writing Skills (CIRC without Picture Series)	29	60	80	65.34	4.211
Pre-Test Writing Skills (Control Class)	17	25	35	27.06	3.561
Post-Test Kete Writing Skills (Control Class)	17	55	65	59.71	3.738
Valid N (listwise)	17				

The test results indicate variations in the improvement of writing ability across each class. The class that implemented the CIRC model with picture media showed the highest improvement, with the average pre-test score increasing from 25.69 to 82.41 in the post-test. Meanwhile, the CIRC class without picture media improved from 28.97 to 65.34, and the conventional class increased from 27.06 to 59.71. Overall, these data indicate differences in the effectiveness of the treatments applied in each class

Furthermore, inferential analysis was conducted to strengthen the results of the descriptive analysis and to obtain more comprehensive and objective conclusions. The

initial stage of this analysis was the normality test, which aimed to determine whether the data in each class were normally distributed or not. The results of the normality test served as the basis for determining the statistical analysis technique used in the subsequent stage. The distribution of data across the three classes can be seen in the following table below :

Table 2. Results of the Shapiro–Wilk Normality Test for Writing Skills.

	Kelas	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-...		
		Stat	df	Sig.	Sta	Df	Sig.
Keterampilan Menulis	Pre-Test Writing Skills (CIRC with Picture Series)	.238	29	<.001	.902	29	.011
	Post-Test Writing Skills (CIRC with Picture Series)	.182	29	.015	.902	29	.011
	Pre-Test Writing Skills (CIRC without Picture Series)	.126	29	.200*	.923	29	.036
	Post-Test Writing Skills (CIRC without Picture Series)	.326	29	<.001	.776	29	<.001
	Pre-Test Writing Skills (Control Class)	.424	17	<.001	.626	17	<.001
	Post-Test Kete Writing Skills (Control Class)	.237	17	.012	.819	17	.004

Because the number of samples in each class was less than 30 ($n < 30$), the normality test was conducted using the Shapiro–Wilk test, which is recommended for small sample sizes. The test was performed at a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$, with the decision criterion that H_0 is rejected when the p-value < 0.05 . The results of the analysis showed that some groups had p-values lower than 0.05, leading to the rejection of H_0 . Therefore, at a 95% confidence level, it can be concluded that the writing skill data in the CIRC class without media and the control class are not normally distributed.

A homogeneity test was conducted to determine the equality of variance among the learning groups. This test employed Levene’s Test, which is commonly used to examine the homogeneity of variances across groups and is sufficiently sensitive to deviations from normal distribution.

Table 3. Homogeneity Test of Writing Skills
Tests of Homogeneity of Variances

		Levene Statistic	df1	df2	Sig.
Writing Skill	Based on Mean	5.585	2	72	.006
	Based on Median	4.294	2	72	.017
	Based on Median and with adjusted df	4.294	2	64.817	.018
	Based on trimmed mean	5.865	2	72	.004

Based on the results of the homogeneity test using Levene’s Test, a p-value > 0.05 was obtained. According to the testing criteria, H_0 is rejected if the p-value < 0.05 . Since the obtained p-value is greater than 0.05, H_0 is accepted. Therefore, based on the mean scores, the writing skill data among the three learning groups are homogeneous.

Table 4 presents the results of the pretest data analysis using the Kruskal–Wallis H Test to determine the differences in initial abilities among the research groups. Based on the calculation results, the following test statistics were obtained.

Table 4. Kruskal–Wallis H Test for Pretest.
Ranks

Kelas		N	Mean Rank
Grade	Pre-Test Writing Skills (CIRC with Picture Series)	29	33.66
	Pre-Test Writing Skills (CIRC without Picture Series)	29	42.74

	Control Class (convensional)	17	37.32
	Sum	75	

Test Statistics^{a,b}
Grade

Kruskal-Wallis H	2.772
Df	2
Asymp. Sig.	.250

Table 5 presents the results of the post-test analysis using the Kruskal–Wallis H test to determine the differences in students’ abilities among the groups after the treatment. The results obtained are presented as follows:

Table 5. Kruskal–Wallis H Test for the Post-test Ranks

	Kelas	N	Mean Rank
Grade	Post Test Writing Skills (CIRC with Picture Series)	29	60.48
	Post Test Writing Skills (CIRC without Picture Series)	29	29.69
	Control Class (convensional)	17	13.82
	Total	75	

Test Statistics^{a,b}
Grade

Kruskal-Wallis H	57.925
Df	2
Asymp. Sig.	<.001

The table shows a clear difference between the pretest and posttest conditions across the three classes. The pretest data indicate a significance value of $0.250 > 0.05$ with a Kruskal–Wallis H value of 2.772, suggesting that there was no significant difference in the initial conditions among the groups. However, after the treatment was administered, the posttest results show a significance value of $0.001 < 0.05$ with a Kruskal–Wallis H value of 57.925. This finding indicates that there were significant differences in students’ writing skill outcomes after the treatment was implemented.

The following table presents a statistical analysis description of students’ self-efficacy, with the results as follows:

Tabel 6 Deskriptif Statistik Efikasi Diri
Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Post-Test Self-Efficacy (CIRC with Picture Series)	29	60	73	67.66	2.869
Post-Test Self-Efficacy (CIRC without Picture Series)	29	59	77	64.00	3.306
Post-Test Self-Efficacy (Control Group)	17	56	63	58.59	2.623
Valid N (listwise)	17				

Based on the results of the study, it was found that each class showed a significant difference between the conditions before and after the treatment. These differences can be observed from the mean post-test scores of each learning group. The class that applied the Cooperative Integrated Reading and Composition (CIRC) model with picture series media obtained a mean score of 67.66, while the class that implemented the CIRC model without

media obtained a mean score of 64.00. Meanwhile, the class that received conventional instruction obtained a mean post-test score of 58.59. In general, these results indicate differences in learning outcomes based on the instructional models applied.

The initial stage of the data analysis was conducted through a normality test to determine whether the data from each class were normally distributed. This test is important as a basis for determining the appropriate statistical analysis techniques to be used in the subsequent analysis. The results of the normality test for the three classes are presented in the following section

Table 7. Results of the Self-Efficacy Normality Test
Tests of Normality

Class		Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk	
		Stat	df	Sig.	Stat	Df
Self-Efficacy	Post-Test Self-Efficacy (CIRC with Picture Series)	.203	29	.004	.892	29
	Post-Test Self-Efficacy (CIRC without Picture Series)	.209	29	.002	.792	29
	Post-Test Self-Efficacy (Control Group)	.250	17	.006	.830	17

Based on the table above, the results of the normality test are presented using the Kolmogorov–Smirnov and Shapiro–Wilk tests. Since the sample size in this study is ≤ 50 , the Shapiro–Wilk test was used because it is more sensitive in detecting deviations from normality. The determination of data normality is based on the significance value (p-value), where a significance value greater than 0.05 indicates that the data are normally distributed, while a significance value less than 0.05 indicates that the data are not normally distributed. Based on these results, the CIRC class without media obtained a significance value (p-value) < 0.05 ; therefore, it can be concluded that the data in this class are not normally distributed.

Furthermore, a homogeneity test was conducted to determine whether the self-efficacy scores across the learning groups had equal variance (homogeneous). In this study, the homogeneity test was performed using Levene’s Test, which is commonly used to examine the equality of variances among groups and is relatively robust against deviations from normal distribution.

Table 8. Results of the Self-Efficacy Homogeneity Test

		Levene Statistic	df1	df2	Sig.
Self-Efficacy	Based on Mean	.258	2	72	.773
	Based on Median	.244	2	72	.784
	Based on Median and with adjusted df	.244	2	59.905	.784
	Based on trimmed mean	.211	2	72	.810

Based on the results of the homogeneity test using Levene’s Test, a p-value > 0.05 was obtained. This indicates that the variance of the self-efficacy data across the three learning groups is homogeneous. However, based on the results of the prerequisite analysis, it was found that the self-efficacy data were not normally distributed. Therefore, the assumption for using parametric tests such as the One-Way ANOVA was not met. Consequently, hypothesis testing in this study was conducted using the non-parametric Kruskal–Wallis H Test.

Table 10 presents the results of the self-efficacy hypothesis test using the Kruskal–Wallis H Test, with the results shown as follows :

Table 9 Kruskal Wallis H Test
Ranks

Class	N	Mean Rank
Grade Post Test Efikasi Diri Kelas CIRC Bergambar	29	56.74
Post Test Efikasi Diri Kelas CIRC tanpaGambar	29	34.45
Post Test Efikasi Diri Kelas Kontrol	17	12.09
Total	75	

Test Statistics^{a,b}
Class

Kruskal-Wallis H	46.611
Df	2
Asymp. Sig.	<.001

Based on the figure, the post-test results show a significance value of 0.001 (< 0.05) with a Kruskal–Wallis H value of 46.611. These results indicate that there is a significant difference in students’ self-efficacy after the treatment across the respective classes.

Discussion

Differences between CIRC with Media, CIRC without Media, and Conventional Instruction on Writing Skills

The results of the study indicate that the Cooperative Integrated Reading and Composition (CIRC) model assisted by picture series media produced the most significant improvement in students’ writing skills compared to CIRC without media and conventional instruction. The mean score of the CIRC class with media increased from 25.69 to 82.41; the CIRC class without media increased from 28.97 to 65.34; and the conventional class increased from 27.06 to 59.71. Conceptually, writing skills encompass five main components: content, organization, vocabulary, grammar, and mechanics (Benyahia, 2025). The superiority of CIRC with media indicates that the integration of cooperative learning and visual support can optimize these five indicators in an integrated manner (Mustainah et al., 2023).

This effectiveness is supported by the systematic syntax of the CIRC model, which includes the formation of heterogeneous groups, reading and comprehension, idea discussion, drafting, revision–editing, and presentation/reflection. These stages are consistent with the writing process theory proposed by Flower and Hayes (1981), which emphasizes the stages of planning, drafting, and revising (Latif, 2022), as well as the process writing approach (Hyland, 2019). Collaboration and peer feedback strengthen the development of text content and organization. As emphasized by Utami et al. (2021), collaborative strategies improve the quality of text structure and the richness of details in students’ writing. From the perspective of Vygotsky’s social constructivism, group interaction helps students improve grammar and enrich vocabulary through social scaffolding (Zhao, 2024).

The role of picture series media further strengthens these findings. Based on the Multimedia Learning Theory (Mayer & Fiorella, 2022), the combination of visual and verbal elements balances cognitive load and clarifies the organization of the text. Visual prompts have been proven to enhance coherence and the richness of content in students’ writing. Although CIRC without media remains effective due to its cooperative structure, it is less optimal in enriching content without visual stimuli (Fitria, 2024). In contrast, conventional instruction, which involves minimal collaboration, shows the lowest improvement. This finding is consistent with previous research indicating that limited

discussion restricts the development of linguistic quality and text structure (Sukiastini et al., 2013).

Differences Between CIRC with Media, CIRC without Media, and Conventional Learning on Self-Efficacy

In terms of self-efficacy, the CIRC class using picture series media obtained the highest score (67.66), followed by the CIRC class without media (64.00), and the conventional class (58.59). These findings indicate that both the instructional model and the use of media play an important role in shaping students' self-confidence. According to Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory, self-efficacy influences the choice of strategies, persistence, and academic achievement (Bakdoolot et al., 2024). Self-efficacy develops through learning experiences, social support, and the successful experiences achieved by students (Susanti & Marsinun, 2023).

The CIRC syntax with media—goal orientation, heterogeneous group work, picture-based reading, discussion, gradual drafting (scaffolding), peer review, presentation, and reflection—directly strengthens mastery experience, vicarious experience, and verbal persuasion. Verbal support during discussions reinforces the strength indicator (Aikens & Kulacki, 2023), while visualization helps reduce anxiety and increase confidence (Makhmuuda & Afrida, 2025). Multimedia theory also explains that the integration of visual and verbal elements enhances students' sense of capability (Mayer & Fiorella, 2022), and previous studies show that visual media significantly improve self-efficacy (Virdaus & Rifa, 2025).

CIRC without media still improves self-efficacy through group discussions that support the dimensions of magnitude, strength, and generality (Fitria, 2024). However, the impact tends to be less evenly distributed among lower-ability students due to the limited visual stimulus (Tamrin et al., 2011). Meanwhile, conventional teacher-centered instruction restricts active participation, resulting in lower development of self-efficacy (Rizky, 2024). Overall, CIRC with picture series media is the most effective approach because it integrates collaboration, visual scaffolding, and meaningful learning experiences that comprehensively strengthen students' self-efficacy.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the study conducted at SMK Negeri 3 Kepahiang, it can be concluded that there are significant differences among the implementation of the Cooperative Integrated Reading and Composition (CIRC) model with picture series media, CIRC without media, and conventional learning. These differences are evident both descriptively and through statistical analysis after the treatments were administered. Therefore, it can be confirmed that the three instructional models produce significantly different outcomes, and the hypothesis stating that there are differences among the models is accepted.

More specifically, the CIRC model with picture series media demonstrated the most optimal results compared to the other two models. The integration of cooperative learning and visual support creates a learning process that is more active, systematic, and meaningful. CIRC without media still produced better outcomes than conventional learning, although its effectiveness did not reach that of CIRC with media. Meanwhile, conventional learning showed the lowest results, indicating that teacher-centered approaches are less supportive of interaction and collaborative knowledge construction. Therefore, the CIRC model assisted by picture series media is recommended as a more effective instructional strategy in English language learning.

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